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ANATHATIA

world economy technological developments with together , important changes face gave in the economy developments brought news in sports important to changes take came Sports economic developments near watching to go and corporate structure new economic to the rules suitable respectively in order put necessary

Man needs satisfy point of view in terms of important to the function have the sport that is today in the day as an economic element our to us is coming Sports, socio-economic and society features with economic of changes the most important actors to the line to enter continue is doing Societies of sports this economic structure from the feature benefit get for measures is seeing Sports services ; individual, corporate and organization in the form of sports economy own place occupied is different of services work release and consumption point of view in terms of important factor as it seems

This of sports services in research work release , consumption , change and distribution such as economy concepts with has been to relations attention focused on sports services common economy inside apparently stopping passed .

Keywords : Economy , sport, service , production production , consumption, sports market , economic growth, development .

ENTER

A social institute as of sports economic and cultural organizations inside each past in days grow up going structure , this social event of the world variable economic and social conditions in consideration taken again be evaluated necessary by doing puts Sport, of itself except another fields with connection through harvest has been effect of the whole doer and affective one is part of Market economy and international competition conditions judgment push of the world one market to the case to be brought in the process of sports share takes

Today's daily sports, personal and social health keeper and developing features with important one service sector is recognized as Also today in the day public information tools and in particular , the media effect with useful advertisements and promotion tool as a sport, one from the side wide the masses attraction who does show and entertainment activity as consumption sector has become if , another from the side entrepreneurs for big amount financial actions happening interesting economic activity to the field rotation can Industry from the revolution after of people economic in terms of developments , more empty time to find , big of competitions the importance of sports in education role and of people to peace has been dreams of sports diary in life necessity shows . Last in years communication in the field surface came technological developments sports separately one to the industry turned

Sports market or sector very wide and various sports activities own into received product and services is the market . This sector learning in the process of sports feature based on differences with together with the sports market structure with depends the existence of differences as well

from the point of view outside not stay need Therefore , the sport with depends market in the analyses issue different from the points seeing exit and evaluation important important have Sports activities economic of the circle in the analysis , general acceptance done and in literature discussion done different approaches there is . This approaches , or micro economic , or macro economic , or interdisciplinary basically done is increased . Sports activities empty the time evaluation of the sector one small market as when viewed , problem of sports collective one product or service as to society how present to be done with depends . In this case , to sports activities participants important important have that it was because in the sports market efficiency and equality increase in order to state intervention or in order put (other words with so to speak macro policies) necessary will be Other on the other hand , sports commerce activity as when seen , this sports product in the sector or services work issuer firms (i.e clubs) with this product or services consumption doer (ie audience) behavior analysis is being done . This in the approach traditional micro economic (or business economy) techniques and principles is used . With that together , the sports market commerce or in public sports activities used sports materials (sports clothes , sports shoes and sports equipment as) small sector point of view is being studied from the point of view .

This is the view in terms of sports done investments persons for empty the time assessment , rest and entertainment such as from needs besides , education , health and cultural also provide services reach in the sense of to say can Many sports activities are material or service features in terms of economy with closely depend Sports facilities , sports publications , sports equipment , sports tourism , sports clothes such as many areas sports and the economy unites

In sports services work release

Today's daily sports, personal and social health keeper and developing features with important one service sector is recognized as Also today in the day public information tools and in particular , media effect with useful advertisements and promotion tool as a sport, one from the side wide the masses attraction who does show and entertainment activity as consumption sector has become if , another from the side entrepreneurs for big amount financial actions happening interesting economic activity to the field rotation can Sports and service work release in terms of goods work release and consumption sectors come Outgoing , Entrepreneurship and Sports Entrepreneurship sciences and sports economy of science research topic is considered

Sports organizations and of services to the public to be delivered many countries usually state services as done is increasing . Undoubtedly , historical process during of the state perform necessary has been education , health , safety such as duties constant changes inside was Many in organizations that it was himself in sports organizations showed this change , of countries acceptance done political and economic to systems depends respectively done increased not only of the time brought new needs according to is also being formed . Naturally , modern in the world all economic and social changes sports organizations and it is also seen in organizations .

Sports activities economic of the circle in the analysis , general acceptance done and in literature discussion done different approaches there is . This approaches , or micro economic , or macro economic , or interdisciplinary basically done is increased . Sports activities empty the time evaluation of the sector one small market as when viewed , problem of sports collective one product or service as to society how present to be done with depends . In this case , to sports activities participants important important have that it was because in the sports market efficiency and equality increase in order to state intervention or in order put (other words with so to speak

macro policies) necessary will be Other on the other hand , sports commerce activity as when seen , this sports product in the sector or services work issuer firms (i.e clubs) with this product or services consumption doer (ie audience) behavior analysis is being done . This in approach traditional micro economic (or business economy) techniques and principles is used . With that together , the sports market commerce or in public sports activities used sports materials (sports clothes , sports shoes and sports equipment as) small sector point of view is being studied from the point of view .

Today's daily sports organizations for competition conditions difficulty and of this with together consumers awareness increase such as factors sports services in the field the most ideal healthy service to show provide necessity shows . This the situation another from the side example to bring for , 132 countries of the World Bank between spent in research , well-being in the rating ahead has been and economic in terms of developed in the states service in the sector of workers common work to the power the ratio is between 55-75% that is , that is service of the sector of states in the economy weight high level to be development criterion as acceptance will be done . Service in the sector of products work release , presentation and consumers satisfaction level in the designation some technical and concepts work release from the sector received although - of sports services distinguishable one row features have to be because of service quality increase for some special actions display necessary This features as follows sorting can :

- Sports services physicist to existence depends not to be (abstract to be) ,
- sports services work release and of consumption one of time in itself done increase ,
- Sports services to himself special that it was not and not be saved (only repetition can) ,
- Sports services work release in the process from the customer separate not to be and of services in the presentation important role to play
- Sports service straight away present those who are giving service as a " product " . acceptance not to
- Sports services present those who are sufficiency the purchase effect to do
- Sports services present being carried out to the place arrived to go of convenience the purchase effect to do
- Sports services present being carried out of the facility physicist of appearance the purchase effect to do
- Sports service present being carried out time of the interval the purchase effect to do

The beginning of the 21st century the world to surprise puter developments , discoveries and to organizations witness it has been and is happening This of organizations the most famous and in mind those who remain Olympia games , Medium land the sea games , famous tennis tournaments and etc. Politics , art , environment and many another of issues day order occupied sports in our world important position save is coming

Today's in the day medicine , physics , biotechnology , mathematics , psychology , sociology , textiles and sporting goods industry technological to developments suitable with sports in communication . Visualized contact tools , artificial satellites , television , radio , press tools , newspaper and magazines sports used without to the public is delivering . Famous of teams behind big companies there is . Olympia in their games again companies between big competitions there

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is . 2000 year Olympia of games in China transfer for and West of monopoly China the market take over for passing hot competition and lobby activities spend 150 million dollars on sports and sponsorship relationships open is showing . Companies sports events supported and spent money through and in society positive image showing another from the side benefit they get

In particular , sports developed in the states one industry as to be seen of the concept of marketing in sports development big contribution added . Miller Brewing Company in 1982 by conducted in research 96.3% of the population of America per month one how many times to sports events participation , 70% of television sports events through to see and friends about sports with to talk or from journals and sports news from newspapers observation , more than 40% while per week at least one times to sports events participation determined . Sports Marketing fitness, recreation , health to consumers and these are with depends products , services , people , place and thoughts offer doer one the market This on purpose , sports participant and the audience sports products for offer reach with together with fitness activities for need to be instrument and equipment is also offered will be done . Sports done increase for necessary has been stadium , squash hall , tennis courts and others such as structures for necessary has been materials offer is enough Tennis rackets threads repair , laundry and clubs cleaning such as different service show services offer will be done . Professional athletes using , different to marketing products is achieved . Special sports magazines and the press of companies present reached another events done is increased .

Sports services present of those who do works and actions media ads through in the audience new desires and thrills is waking up . Walking , swimming , walking , fitness, aerobics such as diary of sports society by interest with acceptance of the economy main principle has been supply -demand balance suitable that 's it with together diary to the sports market entrance his opinion wakes up . In particular , fitness studios to the service put and in general when big acceptance to be done this of the thesis correctness confirms . Last ten in sports advertising big development showed . Confidential advertising before doing (through sports advertising to do prohibition because of this confidential way done increased) target advertising to do passed . And this of sports economic interest object as value that it increased shows . Empty time activities expansion , since 1980 after in sports to advertisements permission of sports clubs publication rights to the market release , sponsorship , sports clubs structure to change compulsion such as developments with together money into sports complete entered to be told can

In the field of sports done being increased expenses and from sports income get common in terms of three different way done is increasing . They are:

- Man's to himself special expenses and achieved income ,
- Club or organization by done to be increased expenses and achieved incomes ,
- State , central and local controls through done to be increased expenses and achieved revenues .

Companies marketing through sports one how many from alternatives , from one or of all use can , them as follows explain possible : their own sports clubs organize in active sports events participation reach each what sports event , team , activity or an athlete support (sponsorship own responsibilities get); work in connection help giving various sports organizations create and this to organizations participation reach product and services advertising in doing athletes use

Many sports marketing in the states and sports entrepreneurship oil , forestry and from air freight according to big one to the industry became Today's in the day In America, the sports

industry is the 23rd industry known Canada and Sports Marketing in America through received income (sports shoes , ticket sales , golf clubs , fitness centers and hk) 88.5 billion dollars per year organize is enough

Today's sports economy per day income bringing , states between competition increasing social field as tourism himself in the field is showing . Our country introduction , economy development , new investments reproduction , social prosperity in development attention earned sports tourism big contribution to add is expected . summer and winter sports one at the time conducting tourism in our country season through sports year tall expand can This in the field compliance deficiency , nature wealth with famous in our country big loss as is being evaluated . Sea sports , competitions , skiing and place in mountain sports and the time common to use there is as sports fields , recreation in places to tourism service is doing Also for sports holiday appear is happening To sports centers go sports tourism is forming . Especially in large sports organizations economic , cultural , social relationships one wholeness organize is doing and attention is pulling This circumstances local and international importance did not lose without both athletes and spectators are travelers is considered In stadiums region for prestige , income , production producers for sports equipment , brands and others for sports economy and advertisements is a factor .

Summary

Modern sports economy , economic growth and social development for important factor is considered Sports services in the economy big role play and work seats creates and different in the fields financial currents encourages . Also , sports, public health and well-being increasing , as well as social unity and cultural values in development big important have

Within the sector competition increasingly , sports services offer doer organizations own services quality increase , innovation current reach and customers needs to satisfy aspirations necessary Another one important aspect is the state and private sector between cooperation , this while of sports financial stability provides .

In the future , sports services growth and development of the public to sports interest increase , healthy marriage style promote to do and sports economy stability to provide help to give is expected .

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